

Appendix

ASEAN regulation of migration and human trafficking

The documents were assigned to stages based on the summary presented in table 1 of the article “Embracing human rights norms in non-democratic regional organizations: a case-study of ASEAN”, the September 2025 issue of *International Affairs*, doi: 10.1093/ia/iiaf145).

Year	Document title	Type	Stage
2004	<i>ASEAN Declaration Against Trafficking in Persons Particularly Women and Children</i>	Declaration	Soft endorsement Trafficking in persons is a humanitarian concern, but the declaration does not set any binding commitments
2007	<i>ASEAN Declaration on the Protection and Promotion of the Rights of Migrant Workers</i>	Declaration	Soft endorsement Migrant workers’ rights are acknowledged, but there are no specific enforcement mechanisms
2012	<i>ASEAN Agreement on the Movement of Natural Persons (AMNP)</i>	Agreement	Soft endorsement Primarily focuses on economic cooperation and trade facilitation rather than establishing protections for migrant workers
2015	<i>Kuala Lumpur Declaration on Irregular Movement of Persons</i>	Declaration	Soft endorsement Addresses irregular migration but does not impose obligations on member states
2015	<i>ASEAN Convention Against Trafficking in Persons,</i>	Convention	Norm acceptance

	<i>Especially Women and Children (ACTIP)</i>		A legally binding agreement requiring member states to criminalize human trafficking and protect victims
2015	<i>ASEAN Plan of Action Against Trafficking in Persons Especially Women and Children</i>	Plan of Action	Soft endorsement Establishes a framework for anti-trafficking measures but without strict enforcement mechanisms
2017	<i>ASEAN Consensus on the Protection and Promotion of the Rights of Migrant Workers</i>	Consensus	Norm acceptance ^a Strengthens commitments to migrant worker protections through detailed guidelines or a dispute resolution mechanism
2019	<i>ASEAN Declaration on the Rights of Children in the Context of Migration</i>	Declaration	Soft endorsement Highlights child protection but does not establish binding commitments
2021	<i>ASEAN Plan of Action for Cooperation on Immigration Matters</i>	Plan of Action	Soft endorsement Promotes regional coordination on immigration but does not impose legal obligations
2022	<i>Declaration on Portability of Social Security Benefits for Migrant Workers in ASEAN</i>	Declaration	Soft endorsement Encourages regional cooperation on social security portability but does not enforce legal compliance
2023	<i>ASEAN Multi-Sectoral Work Plan Against Trafficking in Persons (2023–2028)</i>	Work Plan	Norm acceptance Strengthens commitments to migrant worker protections through detailed guidelines, programmes, and redistribution of responsibilities

2023	<i>ASEAN Leaders' Declaration on Combating Trafficking in Persons Caused by the Abuse of Technology</i>	Declaration	Soft endorsement Recognizes technology's role in trafficking but does not mandate specific legal actions
2023	<i>Declaration on the Protection of Migrant Workers and Family Members in Crisis Situations</i>	Declaration	Soft endorsement Acknowledges the need for protection in crises but does not introduce binding commitments

Note:^a The 2017 *Consensus on the Protection and Promotion of the Rights of Migrant Workers* is not as strong as ACTIP. It fits into the norm acceptance stage, as it represents a more substantial commitment than previous agreements on migration. The *Consensus* introduces specific principles and obligations that ASEAN member states agree to uphold, provides detailed guidelines for cooperation between labour-sending and labour-receiving states, and establishes a framework for dispute resolution, labour protection and fair treatment of migrant workers. As such, it operationalizes and institutionalizes the norm within ASEAN's governance structure.